

PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' ORAL COMPETENCE (FOREIGN LANGUAGES)

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Abstract: In world experience, it is generally accepted to use various principles and methods in language learning. Teaching methods are selected, first of all, based on educational goals. At each stage of education, students are designed to master a certain amount of knowledge. This article discusses the problems associated with the development of students' speech competencies in teaching English.

Keywords: competence, method, phonetics, lexis, grammar, stylistics, extra-linguistics.

INTRODUCTION

The basis of the knowledge to be mastered is the language material consisting of phonetic, lexical, grammatical, and information specified in the curriculum. In the educational process, students develop speech skills based on this knowledge.

The issues of developing students' oral speech competence occupy a central place in teaching English, as this language is gaining increasing importance as a means of global communication. In this regard, the lack of a language environment is one of the main factors complicating the process of forming oral communication skills. In regions of Uzbekistan where English is not a native language, students face difficulties in improving pronunciation and accent due to limited opportunities for practical communication.

The importance of motivation and self-awareness among students is also high. During the learning process, some students may not fully appreciate the importance of language learning or adopt the wrong approaches, which may lead to a decline in

their learning performance. In order to overcome this situation, it is necessary to use innovative and effective teaching methodologies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Methodological issues also complicate the teaching process, as traditional approaches sometimes fail to meet the requirements of modern education. Therefore, it is necessary to open up the frontiers for the development of students' speech competencies through interactive methods, the unsurpassed dominance of technology, and integration with authentic pedagogical materials. These approaches serve to increase the naturalness, richness, and fluency of students' speech.

The professional qualifications of teachers are important in these processes. Teachers' knowledge of modern pedagogical technologies and their effective use in their lessons can directly affect student results. It is necessary to constantly focus on practice through interactive exercises, games, and discussions by improving teaching methods.

Also, the use of language exchange programs and modern platforms for direct communication creates more favorable conditions for students. As a result, students should become active participants in the language learning process and thus have the opportunity to effectively develop their speech competencies. To address these issues, it is necessary to support individual approaches in the education system as a whole and create accessible conditions for students.

The famous psychologist I.A. Zimnyaya defines it as “the achievement of high perfection of actions and automation of speech processes as a result of training” [Zimnyaya, 1998, 127-b]. We know that in traditional education, much attention was paid to teaching English grammar and vocabulary. Today, in addition to teaching the grammar and vocabulary of the language being studied, language learners are also developing their speech competencies. Now language learners need to master speech competencies, in particular, reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking competencies. Here we will dwell on speech competence.

“Competence” is derived from the Latin word and means “suitable for one’s profession, qualified, worthy”. Competence is the ability to independently and creatively apply in practice a set of knowledge and skills, qualifications and personal qualities, and the acquired theoretical knowledge [Djuraev et al., 2008].

The concept of competence was first used in linguistics by N. Chomsky in the mid-20th century, and was noted as “a set of knowledge, skills and abilities directed towards activity” in the process of using language [Zimnyaya, 2003].

The given explanations make it appropriate to understand the word competence in the field of education as competence, and the competency-based approach to education as an educational direction aimed at the formation of abilities to practically apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in one's personal, professional and social activities. The competency-based approach to language education aims to develop the skills of learners to use the language materials they are learning and the information they have received in their daily lives, to express their thoughts independently in oral and written form in this language, and to apply it appropriately in speech situations, that is, to form the ability to use the language purposefully and practically.

Discourse competence consists of the gradual formation of the following four language learning skills: listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing, through which one can understand the speech and messages being conveyed, express one's thoughts and personal views in a monological manner, communicate freely in dialogical conversations, join polylogues, read various texts and works fluently and write them without errors based on the rules of literacy, compose creative texts, and maintain official working papers [Khursanov, 2021].

In order to correctly guide students in the formation and development of speech competencies, it is necessary, first of all, to study the purpose, characteristics, and difficulties and problematic aspects of existing speech acts [Khursanova, 2023]. If these are not taken into account, teaching will not be effective. Below, we will

consider the difficulties and problematic aspects of working on each type of speech competence separately.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teaching listening comprehension is of great importance and is related to other types of speech competence. Listening comprehension, along with speaking, is a type of oral speech activity. Students who do not have difficulty in listening comprehension also have fewer difficulties in speaking. Also, if students can write and read words and sentences correctly when writing, they can recognize them when listening, which helps them listen.

Teaching English listening comprehension has its own difficulties, which can be divided into linguistic, extra-linguistic, and psychological groups [Yokubov, 2011]:

Linguistic difficulties include difficulties that arise in the grammatical, stylistic, lexical, and phonetic areas.

Extra-linguistic difficulties are difficulties that are not related to the language area. For example, the timbre, speed of speech, the student's attention and the number of times he listens to the speech, as well as the presence of supporting tools and meaningful pictures in listening comprehension.

Psychological difficulties include difficulties that are inextricably linked to the psychological characteristics of the listener [Yakubov, 2011].

The development of speaking competence is also important in practical English learning. Using language as a means of communication is achieved through speaking. Today, speaking in practical English is used in all practical English lessons. Difficulties consist in reflecting the specific aspects of monological and polylogical speeches that are most common in speaking competence [Raupova, 2022].

Reading is the process of obtaining information, understanding its content, and perceiving it by reading a familiar or partially unfamiliar text. Reading in higher education institutions has a special feature, it is worked on, and it is developed based on skills, experience, and knowledge from secondary school studies. The following difficulties were identified in teaching students to read:

- unfavorable learning conditions;
- reading speed;
- the student's lack of development of the ability to understand the content in advance;
- complex grammatical structures, turns, constructions in the text;
- the abundance of unfamiliar sentences, etc.

Working on writing competence also has its own challenges. When we work on developing students' writing competences, we need to be able to identify these challenges and develop writing instruction based on them. The most important of the challenges that arise is that most students are unable to express their thoughts in writing.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be noted that the main goal of learning and teaching English is communication, and in this process the need to develop speech competencies is of great importance. This goal can be achieved by using approaches aimed at developing students' oral skills in the learning process, motivation and innovative teaching methods. It is also necessary to create opportunities to strengthen students' communicative abilities by improving the pedagogical skills of teachers and expanding the language environment. Without developing speech competencies, it is impossible to achieve the intended goals of effective use of the English language and communication.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullaeva, B. S., Abdullaev, D., Khursanov, N. I., Kadirova, K. B., & Djuraeva, L. (2024). Modelling Local Item Dependence in Cloze Tests with the Rasch Model: Applying a New Strategy. *International Journal of Language Testing*, 97-103.
2. Djuraev R.Kh. Language teaching methodology / O.K. Tolipov [and others]; edited by T. Sattorov. – T.: Nasir, 2000.

3. Jurayeva, M., Umarova, F., & Kholmurodova, E. (2024). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GENDER APPROACHES IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 15), 707-710.
4. Khursanov NI. The Importance of Testing and Assessment Principles in Modification Process of Exam Tasks. Assessment in Teaching Foreign Languages: Achievements, Challenges and Solutions. *The International Scientific Proceeding Conference*. 2021. April (pp. 9-10).
5. Khursanova L. Pedagogical Methods of Creating Independent Educational Assignments: Didactic Approach. MMIT. 2023 May 25:140-2.
6. Korompot, C. A., Siregar, I., Khursanov, N. I., Abdullaev, D., & Mohamed, K. M. (2024). Investigating Gender DIF in the Reading Comprehension Section of the B2 First Exam. *International Journal of Language Testing*, 14(2), 57-66.
7. Ostonov, O., Khalikova, S., Raimjanova, U., & Umarova, F. (2023). The Role of Historical Knowledge in the Development of Uzbek Tourism. *SGS-Engineering & Sciences*, 2(02).
8. Raupova L., Akhmedova M. Current status and prospects of transition to the credit-module system in the development of students' speech competence in higher philological education. *Bulletin of the National University of Uzbekistan*, 2022, [1/1/2]. 95-97.
9. Yokubov I. *Practical English Methodology*. – T.: Perfect Print, 2011.
10. Zimnyaya I. *Psychological aspects of teaching speaking in a foreign language*. – M.: Moscow State University, 1998. – 142 p.
11. Rahmatullayevich, B. F. (2024). EFFECTIVE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING WITH AN EMPHASIS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS. *THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH*, 3(26), 124-127.

12. Isroilova, B. (2021). FORMATION OF MOTIVATION IN STUDENTS DURING TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE. In *МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 399-401).
13. Panthangi, R. K., Pant, S., Abbas, H. M., Parpiyeva, U., Saparbaeva, N., Sanduru, B., & Kumar, S. (2024). FEA of GTAW process parameters for dissimilar materials of aluminium alloys. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 563, p. 02005). EDP Sciences.
14. Rakhmanov, S., Turaev, K., & Madalieva, D. (2023). Implementation of mathematical models and algorithms in task control of the microalgae cultivation processes. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 377, p. 03010). EDP Sciences.